

Gattulli V., Lofrano E., Paolone A., Potenza F., "Measured properties of structural damping in railway bridge", *Journal of Civil Structural Health Monitoring*, vol. 9(5), pp. 639-653, 2019.

Measured properties of structural damping in railway bridges

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Abstract

Dissipative properties of a structural system are difficult to be characterized in real structure. Nevertheless, damping features may be dominant in several operating conditions of railway bridges influencing fatigue life or passenger comfort during train passage. Observations treating real data acquired in operational condition on steel and concrete railway bridges belonging to the Italian network permits to highlight dissipative sources and features. Consequently, linearized modal damping ratios are evaluated through a recursive process on the acceleration signals acquired before, during and after train passages and/or in environmental conditions. Stochastic Subspace Identification has been used to identify state-space dynamical models able to reproduce the vibrations. Through these models, characterized by an increasing number of state-space variables, it is possible to extract modal damping ratios. A mechanical interpretation of damping characteristics is pursued through the evaluation of the differences with respect to a classical Rayleigh proportional damping matrix of the viscous matrix belonging to the identified state-space models determined through the system spectral features. A non-proportional damping index is presented as a basis to determine the influence of different sources of non-proportionality in the damping matrix (as the ballast layer under the track) and to justify the high value of damping observed in specific experimental campaigns.

Keywords: Structural damping, dynamic identification, non-proportional damping, railway bridges, experimental results, beam bridges

1. Introduction

Structural Identification aims at the evaluation of the parameters and models able to better represent and reproduce the measured structural behaviour of vibrational systems. It is a topic that raised the interest of the scientific community since several years [1, 2]. Structural Identification plays an important role within the Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) process. Indeed, a correct application of the Structural Identification techniques can provide useful predictive models from which assess the health and vulnerability of a structure. Moreover, even using low cost equipment, like wireless sensors networks or integrated fiber optic sensing devices (easily installable for long period) a functional monitoring system can be implemented [3, 4]. A fast and reliable information extraction could help in verifying the operational condition of structures even heavily damaged after catastrophic events as an earthquake [5, 6, 7].

The management and maintenance of the railway bridges can be refined through the installation of SHM systems that have been largely used specially to assess the operational condition of real bridge structures in the last years [8]. A lot of examples have been successfully implemented worldwide in order to attain real time feedback or detect damage [9, 10, 11, 12]. Among the different phases to be executed in the structural health monitoring process, the one related to the data processing is undoubtedly one of the most relevant. In particular, vibrational measurements have to be handled in order to extract of the principal modal parameters such as modal frequencies, modal shapes and damping ratios. As well-known, the knowledge of such values may help for finite element model updating, non-destructive damage detection, reasonably evaluate the safety of a bridge and design a reliable system for vibration mitigation and control. Classical methods used to identify a parametric models need of both experimental response (known also as output) and excitation source (input). In the last decades, techniques based only on the measure of the output have had a large development [13, 14]. They need to acquire only the dynamic experimental response induced by environmental excitation like wind or

traffic loadings. From this point of view, avoiding to set up an experimental equipment to generate an artificial excitation (quite large in real-scale structures) constitutes unquestionably operational, technical and economic advantage [15, 16, 17, 18]. These methods, called in general Operational Modal Analysis techniques, can be grouped in two categories: frequency domain and time domain approach. In the first class two of the procedures largely used are the Enhanced Frequency Domain Decomposition [19] and PolyMAX [20] while in second one a considerable dissemination and application has been attained by the Stochastic Subspace Identification [21]. Some relevant applications can be found in [22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. Furthermore, in [28] is proposed an automated time-domain methodology to identify modal parameters tested numerically and through experimental tests in laboratory and in a railway bridge.

In the last years, railway infrastructures have had a constant improvement also due to a fast development of high-speed trains. In the railway bridge, the material properties and behaviour of the ballast could affect the whole dynamic of the structure. The interaction ballast-structure is still not well-known and for this reason many researchers have conducted interesting scientific activity related to this issue [29, 30, 31]. Of course, the degree of interaction depends on response amplitude directly related to the excitation level. Different studies have indeed measured and identified different values of the modal parameters (especially related to the damping ratio) connected with large vibration amplitude [32, 34, 35]. This interaction influences specially the identification of the damping ratios. Today, the experimental evaluation is the only reliable way to identify the damping. Indeed, an analytical quantification is in general very difficult especially due to the complicated damping mechanisms. In [33] has been recently carried out an extensive experimental campaign to evaluate the main modal frequencies and damping ratios of a wide number of bridge through Operational Modal Analysis. While for fundamental frequencies have been found equation related to the structural characteristics of the bridges, the damping ratios

did not show any connection with the geometric features.

The present work presents a deepening analysis about the dynamic structural behaviour of railway bridges. In detail, it summarizes the results obtained from one-day of experimental tests on two different typologies of railway beam bridges: (1) pre-stressed concrete and (2) steel truss bridge. The fundamental steps carried out to define reliable structural features of the two bridges are described and commented as follows: (1) description of the experimental tests, (2) processing of the response data, (3) model identification and (4) model updating. Regarding the third point, a particular attention is paid to an accurate evaluation of the structural damping. Indeed, the last paragraph is devoted to a mechanical interpretation of damping characteristics pursued through a model-based procedure that aim to evaluate the differences with respect to a classical Rayleigh proportional damping matrix.

2. Dynamic tests on railway bridges

The railway bridges studied in this on-field activity belong to the Italian railway network. In particular, the first one is realized in pre-stressed concrete and it is a part of the high-speed network (Fig 1a-c). Instead, the second one is a steel railway bridge showing a typical truss-configuration (Fig 1d-f).

The first bridge is situated in proximity of Rome, very close to the new station “Ponte Nona”. It is an infrastructure of the line Rome-Naples. As well visible by the photos reported in the Fig 1. a-c it is a girder bridge composed by 4 main reinforced concrete cast-in-place deck on a V-shape girders. These latter elements have been made prefabricated and pre-stressed then have been linked together by 4 cast-in-place cross girders. Other geometrical characteristics describing the general bridge configuration are the following: total length and width are of 621.60 m and 13.60 m, respectively; the bridge is constituted by 24 central spans having a length of 24.00 m to which have to be added the first and last span with a length of 22.80 m. The girder is supported hollow bridge-piers of height variable between 5.00 m and 9.50 m with a transversal

section of 3.60 m x 8.80 m. At the bridge ends the abutments have a height of 4.50 m and 7.00 m respectively for Rome and Naples sides. For both, piers and abutments, the foundations have been realized with a slab anchored to the ground through piles with a diameter of 1.20 m and a variable length (up to the lithoid substrate). The tracks have been made with ballast. A simply supported isostatic beam could be the structural model adoptable for this type of configuration.

The steel railway beam bridge has been realized using a construction technique classically adopted in the early 1970s. Substantially, it is composed by two vertical, longitudinal and parallel truss-girders designed to bear the vertical loads. They are connected together through transverse bracings inserted to the top and base of the same truss-girders. Moreover, some of these elements are disposed perpendicularly while other ones have a cross-configuration. They have been designed for both to confer a high torsional stiffness and improve the transverse stability. Each girder shows five portions with an interval of 9.40 m and a height of 6.80 m. The overall free length is of 47.00 m while the distance between the two main vertical truss-girder is of 5.90 m. The general configuration of the bridge could be well represented by an isostatic scheme of a simply supported beam. Moreover, since the bridge crosses the river obliquely the two truss-girders present a geometric offset of one half sector. This last feature gives to the steel railway bridge a not perfectly symmetrical configuration. The transversal beams are connected in correspondence of the main truss-girder nodes. They support the spars where have been linked the wood transversal beams and the tracks. The transversal cross section of the truss-girder is a double “T” stiffened to the ends by steel plates. A support system has been opportunely inserted at each ends of the truss-girder, fixed on one side and mobile in the other one.

2.1 Description of the experimental tests

The dynamic tests have been carried out in one-day experimental campaign for both bridges. Moreover, the measurements recorded have been the accelerations for both cases. Regarding the concrete railway bridge the acquisition system has been implemented in wired mode while for

Fig 1 Set of photos related to the two railway bridges: (a)-(c) concrete bridge, (d)-(f) steel bridge

Fig 2 Experimental layouts for concrete, (a), and steel (bottom view, b), (lateral view, c), railway bridge

the steel one has been used an acquisition via wireless.

The experimental layout used for the concrete railway bridge was composed by 15 3-axis wired accelerometers (Bridge XP) arranged according to the scheme reported in Fig 2a. The figure shows how the two spans have been both instrumented but in the next subparagraphs only the evidences coming from the recordings attained by the sensors disposed in the left span will be deepened. This is due to reason of writing space. The accelerometric nodes have been collocated on the inner face of the bottom edge. The measurements have been recorded before, after and during the train passage. In particular,

more or less 5 seconds before of the arrival of the train and about 18 seconds after the train passage. Moreover, the accelerations induced by train passages have been acquired in both directions Rome-Naples and Naples-Rome. In Fig 3 have been reported two examples of time histories acquired during the train passages in both directions. In particular, in the Figs. 3a and 3c are illustrated the time histories while in the Figs 3b and 3d are shown the corresponding Fast Fourier Transforms (FFT). Furthermore, the last ones have been calculated processing the accelerations recorded after the train passage (the last 5 seconds). The peaks of both responses are very low, about 0.006 g, probably due to the high train crossing speed. Looking to the FFTs, even though the measurements have been recorded using a sampling frequency of 5000 Hz, it seems difficult to recognize peaks associated to the structural modes. Nevertheless, especially observing the Fig. 2b, the main peaks in correspondence of 8.60 Hz and 10.00 Hz could be related to the principal vibration modes.

Instead, the Fig. 4 illustrates the time histories acquired during the experimental tests on the steel railway bridge. The equipment was constituted by a low-cost WSN whose potentiality and drawbacks have been already verified during the seismic monitoring of a cultural heritage heavily destroyed by the L'Aquila 2009 Earthquake [3]. Each sensor node is constituted by a wireless communication platform (MEMSIC Imote 2), a sensor board (MEMSIC SHM-A) in which have been collocated a low-cost tri-axial MEMS accelerometer (ST microelectronics LIS344LH),

Fig 3 Concrete bridge: time histories (a), (c) and FFT (b), (d) recorded during the train passage for both directions

Fig 4 Steel bridge: time histories (a), (c) and FFT (b), (d) recorded during excitation by small jumps and train passage

a temperature and humidity sensor (Sensirion SHT11) and a luminosity sensor (TAOS 2661). The measurements reported in Fig. 4a have been induced by small transversal jumps aim to activate the main structural modes. The other time history, reported in Fig. 4c, shows the accelerations recorded during the train passage. In the Figs. 4b and 4c are illustrated the corresponding FFTs. The peaks of accelerations are higher compared with the ones of the previous case. In particular, especially the ones induced by the train passage show amplitude

values very close to 0.03 g. They are different of almost an order of magnitude compared with the ones of Fig. 3a and 3c. Looking to the FFTs appears very clearly what are the frequencies' peaks associated to the main structural modes. Moreover, the information coming from both dynamic tests are very close to each other reinforcing the idea that such peaks may be of modal nature. The identified frequencies assume the value of 2.99 Hz and 5.71 Hz respectively for the first mode and the second one.

2.2 Modal identification

This section illustrates a deep investigation on modal identification using a well-known technique working in the time domain: Stochastic Subspace Identification (SSI). Subsequently, the finite element models representative of the railway bridges structural behavior is updated on the basis of the information coming from the identification process.

The first analysis is related to the concrete railway bridge. In this case, to better identify the main vibrational modes, have been processed three sections of the whole time histories acquired during the train passage. The SSI will be performed using different time ranges that are well-visible in the Fig. 3a: (1) “before” in which will be considered the measurements acquired before the train passage (more or less 5 seconds), (2) “after” in which will be processed the accelerations recorded immediately after the train passage (about 15 seconds) and, finally (3) “all” in which will be used the whole time histories recorded (30 seconds). It is evident how in all three sections the ranges are very short not allowing the development of clear stability diagrams from which identifying the frequencies associated to the structural modes. Nevertheless, this separation could be helpful to accurately assess the value of such frequencies. Moreover, each section will be treated also applying the SSI with the modality Reference-based [21] that permits both a reduction of the problem dimensions and of the computational time. In general, in the experimental applications could be used a lot of sensors widely spread over the whole structure. For this reason, some of these could be placed in nodal points of the modal shapes or in points close to fixed boundaries. Consequently, an accurate reduction of the sensors used in the processing is opportune as well as the choice of the reference sensors. Clearly, the information of all modes have to be present in the data measured by the reference nodes. Indeed, if the optimal sensors are selected as reference no loss of identification quality is expected. On the contrary, since the lower quality sensors are partially omitted, the identification results may be more accurate. All results related

to the SSI have been obtained by the software MACEC [36].

As stated before, the results of the SSI, in some cases, are not very good not allowing a correct identification of the modal parameters (indicated with “*n.i.*” in the tables). The poor reliability of the identification is found especially by the imperfect correspondence between the numerical and experimental modal shapes. For this reason, it has been introduced a new coefficient, “*coefficient of similarity*” that compares the numerical and experimental modes only visually. The main two modes for a typical configuration of girder bridge show a bending shape contained in the X-Z plan (where X is the longitudinal direction and Z is transversal axis perpendicular to the plane of the grid, first mode) and torsional along the longitudinal axis (second mode). Based on these observations has been decided to assign a value of the coefficient of similarity according to the indication reported in Table 1.

Coherently, for each mode identified have been assigned a value of such coefficient. Results related to the three time intervals are reported in the following Tables 2, 3 and 4. In each table are reported seven columns: the first one indicates the modality of application of the SSI, in the second and third column are reported the identified modal frequencies for the two main modes, in the fourth and fifth column the modal damping while in the last two columns the value

Table 1 Criteria for assigning the coefficient of similarity

Criteria	Value of the coefficient of similarity, c
Identified modal shape similar to the numerical one. All nodes in phase in the case of the first mode.	1.00
Identified modal shape similar to the numerical one. Only one node is in counterphase.	0.75
Identified modal shape similar to the numerical one. Two or more nodes are in counterphase.	0.50
Identified modal shape dissimilar to the numerical one.	0.25
Modes not identified	0.00

Table 2 Frequency, damping and coefficient of similarity identified using the measurements in the first section (*before*)

SSI/Ref	f_{1c} [Hz]	f_{2c} [Hz]	ξ_{1c} [%]	ξ_{2c} [%]	c_{1c} [-]	c_{2c} [-]
SSI/all nodes	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 1	8.503	10.619	2.805	7.137	0.50	1.00
Ref node 2	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 3	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 4	8.603	10.511	3.257	0.443	1.00	1.00
Ref node 5	8.662	10.968	3.835	5.026	1.00	1.00
Ref node 6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 7	8.624	10.481	2.022	6.692	0.75	1.00

Table 3 Frequency, damping and coefficient of similarity identified using the measurements in the second section (*after*)

SSI/Ref	f_{1c} [Hz]	f_{2c} [Hz]	ξ_{1c} [%]	ξ_{2c} [%]	c_{1c} [-]	c_{2c} [-]
SSI/all nodes	8.860	n.i.	4.450	n.i.	0.50	0.00
Ref node 1	8.800	n.i.	0.690	n.i.	0.25	0.00
Ref node 2	9.060	n.i.	4.600	n.i.	0.25	0.00
Ref node 3	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 4	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	0.00	0.00
Ref node 5	8.140	12.910	1.180	4.250	0.25	0.50
Ref node 6	9.160	11.370	7.440	7.340	0.25	0.50
Ref node 7	8.832	n.i.	3.130	n.i.	0.25	0.00

Table 4 Frequency, damping and coefficient of similarity identified using the measurements in the third section (*all*)

SSI/Ref	f_{1c} [Hz]	f_{2c} [Hz]	ξ_{1c} [%]	ξ_{2c} [%]	c_{1c} [-]	c_{2c} [-]
SSI/all nodes	9.220	11.950	1.600	1.550	0.75	1.00
Ref node 1	8.760	12.870	0.882	3.620	1.00	0.75
Ref node 2	8.850	13.610	3.400	1.400	0.75	0.75
Ref node 3	8.640	12.170	2.760	2.400	0.75	1.00
Ref node 4	8.850	11.830	3.740	3.680	1.00	1.00
Ref node 5	8.790	12.780	0.830	4.740	1.00	0.75
Ref node 6	9.080	12.110	2.490	4.450	0.75	1.00
Ref node 7	9.110	11.970	0.330	4.870	0.75	1.00

of the coefficient of similarity for the first and second mode, respectively. Looking at the results reported in the three tables, it appears immediately evident how the worst identification has been found during the processing of the signals belonging to the time window “*after*”. Indeed, in this case there are two attempts to

identify modes completely failed in correspondence of the modality *Ref node 3* and *Ref node 4*. Moreover, only in the identification through *Ref node 5* and *Ref node 6* has been possible to recognize both principal modes (in terms of modal frequencies, shapes and damping). Instead, in several cases only the first

mode has been identified showing a modal shape very different from the numerical one (very low values of the coefficient of similarity). The Table 2 is related to the identification attained with the recordings in time window “before” where the overview of the results is slightly better. Indeed, even though there are a lot of cases (among which also the SSI/all nodes) in which the identification is completely failed, in the other ones have been found all two main modes. Furthermore, the modal shapes identified seems to be very close to the numerical ones especially in correspondence of the processing *Ref node 4* and *Ref node 5* where the value of the coefficient of similarity is equal to 1 for both modes. The best identification results have been obtained when all the measured time histories have been processed (Table 4). This good scenario could be due substantially of two factors: first, the section “all” is longer compared to the other two and, second, it shows accelerations amplitude higher respect to the other two sections. Moreover, the coefficients of similarity are all between 1.00 and

0.75 thus showing a good agreement between numerical and experimental modes.

In order to better visualize the modal shapes, in Fig 5 the results of the two processing (*Ref node 4* in Table 2 and 4) are reported confirming that this cases furnish the modal shapes more easily interpretable with a mechanical finite element model. In particular, the Fig 5a and 5d illustrate the stability diagrams obtained elaborating the signal in the time windows “before” and “all”, respectively. Looking at this two graphs it is easily verifiable how the one in correspondence of the section “all” (Fig. 5d) can give more robust information. Indeed, it shows stable poles more close at the identified frequencies while in the diagram reported in Fig. 5a such poles seem to have a wider spread around the range of frequencies considered (more or less 7-18 Hz). Moreover, in the Fig. 5d the stable poles are found in correspondence of the power spectral densities’ peaks inserted in the diagram background.

Fig 5 Stability diagrams (Reference based with the node 4) determined using measurements before the train passage (a) and the whole time histories (d). Modal shapes for the stability diagram in fig 5a, (b), (c), and fig 5d, (e), (f)

Table 5 Concrete bridge: Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) between the modes identified in Fig 5 and the numerical ones in Fig 8

Modes	Mode 1 (Ref 4, before)	Mode 2 (Ref 4, before)	Mode 1 (Ref 4, all)	Mode 2 (Ref 4, all)
Mode 1, numerical	0.8447	0.0006	0.9311	0.0183
Mode 2, numerical	0.0485	0.7976	0.0182	0.8771

The modal frequencies identified through the two processing are 8.603 Hz and 8.850 Hz for the first mode and 10.511 Hz and 11.830 Hz for second mode. Regarding the first frequency the difference is very low (2.87 %) while for the second one seems to be too high (12.55 %). Nevertheless, the one in correspondence of the diagram *Ref node 4/all* (i.e. the graph in Fig. 5f) appears more consistent with a torsional shape along the longitudinal axis X. Indeed, especially the modal displacement of the node 4 shows a higher Z-component than the one in Fig. 5c conferring an effect of greater torsionality at the second modal shape. Same observation can be made for the first mode looking at the modal displacement of the node 3. Even in this case the Z-component is higher than the one in Fig. 5b. For these reasons, the better identified modes are the ones shown in the Figs. 5e and 5f. Moreover, to better consolidate such observation, have been calculated the Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) between the two coupled of modes reported in the Figs. 5a, 5b, 5e, and 5f. The results illustrated in Table 5 shows how the modal shapes obtained with the modality *Ref/all* are the ones that better match with the numerical modes. The same procedure has been applied for identifying the principal modes involved in the dynamics response of the steel railway bridge. Indeed, in Table 6 the results obtained processing the measurements induced by small jumps through SSI and SSI/ref have been reported. In particular, in the first column have been indicated the modalities of application while in the others ones have been pointed out the first three modal

frequencies (second-fourth column) and damping (fifth-seventh column). The identified quantities appear very stable reaching such average values (reported in the last row of the Table 6): 2.979 Hz for the first frequency and 5.721 Hz and 5.884 Hz for the second and third frequency, respectively. The average modal dampings are 0.195%, 0.580% and 0.874% for the first, second and third mode, respectively. This topology of steel bridge shows a behavior more flexible than the previous one in concrete. Moreover, the second and third frequencies are very close to each other making very difficult a correct identification of such modes. Furthermore, the modal dampings assume very low values below the 1%. In Figs. 6a and 6b are illustrated two examples of stability diagrams obtained applying the *SSI/all nodes* and *SSI Ref node 11*. They show a very clear and stable behavior specially in the second case *Ref node 11*. It is worth to notice that the presence of the two modal frequencies around 5.70 Hz and 5.90 Hz occur going towards model orders higher than 30. In the right part of the same figure (Figs. 6c, 6d and 6e) are reported the corresponding modal shapes. All modes have been represented through a view from above. The first mode shows a bending shape outside from its vertical plane as expected with a slight misalignment for the nodes 3 and 8. Indeed, as they are collocated, more or less, in the midpoint they should have the largest out of plane deflection. Also the second and third mode exhibit a bending shape but with the presence of a zero-modal point between the nodes 2 and 3.

Table 6 Frequency, damping identified using the measurements obtained exciting the structure through small jumps. Steel Bridge

SSI/Ref	f_{1c} [Hz]	f_{2c} [Hz]	f_{3c} [Hz]	ξ_{1c} [%]	ξ_{2c} [%]	ξ_{3c} [%]
SSI/all nodes	2.976	5.682	5.924	0.168	0.991	2.686
Ref node 1	2.982	5.719	5.876	0.187	0.385	0.762
Ref node 2	2.982	5.719	5.877	0.181	0.416	0.787
Ref node 3	2.982	5.716	5.875	0.180	0.386	0.795
Ref node 4	2.967	n.i.	5.861	0.092	n.i.	0.043
Ref node 6	2.981	5.718	5.912	0.225	0.376	0.338
Ref node 11	2.982	5.748	5.874	0.273	0.827	0.808
Ref node 12	2.982	5.748	5.875	0.251	0.676	0.773
Mean	2.979	5.721	5.884	0.195	0.580	0.874

Fig 6 Stability diagrams (Reference based with the node 11) determined using measurements induced by small jumps (a), (b). Main modal shapes selected through the stability diagrams (c) mode 1 (d) mode 2 (e) mode 3

Fig 7 Lateral view of main modal shapes selected through the stability diagrams (c) mode 1 (d) mode 2 (e) mode 3

It is worth to highlight that a counter phase displacement is observed in the node 7 compared to the node 2. This occurrence makes the alignment of the nodes 7-8-9 different from the one of the nodes 2-3-4. Indeed, also between the nodes 7 and 8, a zero-modal point was expected. In Fig. 7 have been reported the same modal shapes illustrated in the Figs. 6c, 6d and 6e in lateral view. Indeed, in the identification process have been used both transversal measurements in Y-direction (out of plane) and Z-direction (in plane). As well visible specially in the Figs. 7b and 7c, the second and third mode show high values of the modal components putting into

evidence an important torsional effect for such modes.

2.3 Finite element models updating

To better understand the dynamic behavior of the railway bridges in this section are described the modal characteristics of predicted and update finite element models for both cases.

The concrete railway bridge model has been realized through the software SAP2000. In order to better discretize the single span of the bridge has been chosen to represent the structural behavior using shell elements. In Fig. 8a has been reported an image of 3D numerical model implemented using such finite elements. The model faithfully reports the geometry of the structure that includes 4 prefabricated and prestressed beams that are linked together by 4 cast-in-place cross girders. Moreover, all these elements are filleted by a collaborating concrete slab. The constitutive law of the material has an elastic and linear behavior. In order to improve the dynamic behavior of the numerical model have been carried out a tuning of the elastic

Table 7 Concrete railway bridge: Experimental vs. Numerical modal frequencies

Mode	Exp. [Hz]	Num. [Hz]	Δ %
1	8.850	8.939	1.006
2	11.830	10.653	-9.949

modulus and of the restraints distribution at the ends of the beam to make as close as possible the numerical modes with the experimental ones. The final values of the elastic moduli for the slab and beams are 33346 N/mm^2 and 35000 N/mm^2 , respectively, while the Poisson ratio is equal to 0.2 for both. Regarding the restraints distribution, a symmetric configuration has been adopted in which the two central beams have been fixed in all three translational directions while for the external ones have been released the longitudinal direction. The actual restraints distribution are illustrated in Fig. 7b in which the red triangle indicates the lock of the all three translational directions while the red circle indicates the release in the longitudinal one (highlighted in the Figure with the numbers “2” and “1”, respectively). A comparison between the experimental and numerical frequencies is reported in Table 7. The result seems quite good especially for the first mode where the difference is of the one percent. A more important difference is shown for the second mode (near to 10%) due to a higher difficulty in the identification of a correct and reliable frequency. In any case there is a perfect similarity between the experimental and numerical modal shapes for both modes.

The numerical model representative of the steel railway bridge has been implemented using the software Midas Gen. In this case the structural behavior has been modelled through mono-dimensional elements for which the constitutive law of the material has been chosen elastic and linear. Moreover, the elastic modulus and

Poisson’s coefficient has been chosen equal to the nominal values of the steel: 210000 N/mm^2 and 0.3, respectively. The shapes of the transverse sections have been selected in according with the design drawings. Regarding the boundaries have been fixed the displacements of the external nodes of the main bottom external beams. In the Fig. 9a is illustrated a 3D view of the numerical model. Instead, in the Figs. 9b, 9c e 9d have been shown the first three modal shapes and the related frequencies mainly involved in the structural dynamic response. The comparison between the experimentally identified and numerical modal frequencies appears very good looking at the results reported in the Table 8. Indeed, for all three modes the percentage difference is less than 4%. Some differences have been found in the modal shapes, especially for the second and third mode. Indeed, for these two identified modes, some the transversal and lateral modal displacements seem to be in counterphase: node 7 for both modes and node 2 for the third mode. In any case, the level of improvement of the numerical model can be considered acceptable.

Table 8 Steel railway bridge: Experimental vs. Numerical modal frequencies

Mode	Exp. [Hz]	Num. [Hz]	Δ %
1	2.979	2.911	-2.283
2	5.721	5.923	3.531
3	5.884	5.980	1.632

Fig 8 Finite Element Model for the concrete bridge: (a) 3D view of numerical model, (b) distribution of the restraints: “1” fixed u_x and u_y , “2” fixed u_x , u_y and u_z , (c) and (d) first two main numerical modes

Fig 9 Finite Element model for the steel bridge: (a) 3D view; modal shape for the (b) first, (c) second and (d) third mode

3. Features of damping sources

Usual railway bridges are built of slender one-dimensional elements or their assemblages, which behavior can be properly described through a beam model with negligible shear effect. On the other hand, the most widespread structural scheme in railway network is a statically determinate scheme with continuous track. Accordingly, to this discussion, beam bridges are here modelled as simply supported Euler-Bernoulli beams. The purpose of this formulation is to recognize the sources of damping characteristics, evaluating the ratio among proportional and non-proportional contributions, where the latter is introduced via Kelvin-Voigt like end devices. The first two subparagraphs are dedicated to the description of the model, whereas in the third one the method is applied to the case studies presented above, which results are shown in the last paragraph.

3.1 Field equation

The free flexural vibrations for an undamped Euler-Bernoulli beam are governed by the field equation (see Fig. 10):

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left[B(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right] + \mu(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$x \in [0, L]$

being x the local abscissa along the beam length L , $v(x,t)$ the kinematic descriptor (transversal displacement), t the time, $B(x)=E(x)I(x)$ the flexural stiffness (with $E(x)$ the Young's modulus of the material and $I(x)$ the moment of inertia of the cross section), and $\mu(x)=\rho(x)A(x)$ the mass per unit length (with $\rho(x)$ the density of the material and $A(x)$ the area of the cross section).

Fig 10 Variables of the beam model ($c(x)=0$ for the undamped case)

Eq. (1) is a Partial Differential Equation PDE, which solution could be, in general, not straightforward. In this work, the beam shape is assumed prismatic, and the material properties homogeneous, that is:

$$v(x,t)'''' + \frac{\mu}{B} \ddot{v}(x,t) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$x \in [0, L], \quad \frac{\partial^*}{\partial x} = *', \quad \frac{\partial^*}{\partial t} = *\dot{}$$

where the ratio μ / B is a constant. The solution $v(x,t)$ of Eq. (2) can be found adopting the typical

time-space decomposition of the variables (modal approach):

$$v(x,t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \phi_i(x) q_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_i(x)$ is the i -th mode-shapes and $q_i(t)$ the time-history of the relevant modal coordinates. The modal decomposition Eq. (3) leads the governing Eq. (2) to:

$$\phi_i^{(4)}(x) q_i(t) + \frac{\mu}{B} \phi_i(x) \ddot{q}_i(t) = 0, \forall x, t, i \quad (4)$$

from which:

$$\frac{\phi_i^{(4)}(x)}{\phi_i(x)} = -\frac{\mu}{B} \frac{\ddot{q}_i(t)}{q_i(t)} = \lambda_i^4 \quad (5)$$

where the separation variable λ_i is an unknown constant. Eq. (5) is an eigenvalue problem that admits the well-known solution:

$$\phi_i(x) = A_{1i} \cos(\lambda_i x) + A_{2i} \cosh(\lambda_i x) + A_{3i} \sin(\lambda_i x) + A_{4i} \sinh(\lambda_i x) \quad (6a)$$

$$q_i(t) = A_{5i} e^{\Lambda_i t}, \quad \lambda_i^4 = -\frac{\mu}{B} \Lambda_i^2 \quad (6b)$$

being $\phi_i(x)$ the i -th eigenfunction (the i -th mode-shape) and Λ_i the relevant i -th eigenvalue.

When damping is considered, the free flexural vibrations in Eq. (1) need to be accordingly updated:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left[B(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \right] + c(x) \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial t} + \mu(x) \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad x \in [0, L] \quad (7)$$

where $c(x)$ is the coefficient of external (linearly viscous) damping (any other source of damping is assumed negligible here), see Fig. 10.

Under the assumptions of prismatic beam shape and homogeneous material properties, the three quantities $B(x)$, $c(x)$ and $\mu(x)$ have constant value, and the governing equation becomes the following one:

$$v(x,t)^{(4)} + \frac{c}{B} \dot{v}(x,t) + \frac{\mu}{B} \ddot{v}(x,t) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$x \in [0, L], \quad \frac{\partial^*}{\partial x} = *', \quad \frac{\partial^*}{\partial t} = \dot{*}$$

The adoption of the modal decomposition Eq. (3), with $\phi_i(x)$ as in Eq. (6), leads the Eq. (8) to:

$$\ddot{q}_i(t) + \frac{c}{\mu} \dot{q}_i(t) + \frac{B}{\mu} \lambda_i^4 q_i(t) = 0 \quad (9)$$

From a physical point of view, the external damping does not alter the mode-shape of vibrations; however, the relations among eigenvalue Λ_i and separation variable λ_i become:

$$\phi_i(x) = A_{1i} \cos(\lambda_i x) + A_{2i} \cosh(\lambda_i x) + A_{3i} \sin(\lambda_i x) + A_{4i} \sinh(\lambda_i x) \quad (10)$$

$$q_i(t) = A_{5i} e^{\Lambda_i t}, \quad \lambda_i^4 = -\frac{\mu}{B} \Lambda_i^2 - \frac{c}{B} \Lambda_i$$

where Eq. (6) can be obtained placing the damping c equal to zero.

The eigenvalue Λ_i and three relations among the four constants A_{1i} , A_{2i} , A_{3i} and A_{4i} (the last one playing the role of the generic constant scaling the amplitude) are evaluated imposing the four boundary conditions (two for each edge). A_{5i} is provided by the initial conditions (on displacement $v(x,t)$ and velocity $\partial v(x,t)/\partial t$).

3.2 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions alternatives are described in terms of the kinematic parameter $v(x,t)$ as:

- displacement restrained: $v(x,t)|_{x=X} = V_X$
- displacement free: $-B \partial^3 v(x,t)/\partial x^3|_{x=X} = H F_X$
- rotation restrained: $\partial v(x,t)/\partial x|_{x=X} = \theta_X$
- rotation free: $B \partial^2 v(x,t)/\partial x^2|_{x=X} = H M_X$ (11)

where $X=\{0,L\}$, $H=-1$ in $x=0$ and $H=1$ in $x=L$; the right-hand side quantities are the imposed values of displacement (V_X), force (F_X), rotation (θ_X) and moment (M_X), see Figs. 11a, 11b.

In this work, viscoelastic (Kelvin-Voigt like) devices are considered at the beam ends. In this case, the force $H F_X$ and the moment $H M_X$ must be updated to consider the restoring forces of the devices:

$$\begin{aligned}
& v(x,t)|_{x=X} = V_X \\
& -B \frac{\partial v^3(x,t)}{\partial x^3} \Big|_{x=X} = \\
& = H \left(F_X - K_{TX} v(x,t) \Big|_{x=X} - C_{TX} \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial t} \Big|_{x=X} \right) \\
& \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=X} = \theta_X \\
& B \frac{\partial v^2(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \Big|_{x=X} = \\
& = H \left(M_X - K_{RX} \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=X} - C_{RX} \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x \partial t} \Big|_{x=X} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

being K_{TX} (C_{TX}) the stiffness (damping) of the transversal springs (dashpots), and K_{RX} (C_{RX}) the stiffness (damping) of the rotational springs (dashpots), see Fig. 2c.

Imposing the boundary conditions Eq. (12) into the eigensolution Eq. (10) allows to evaluate the eigenvalue Λ_i and three relations among the four constants C_{1i} , C_{2i} , C_{3i} and C_{4i} (ruling the shape of the eigenfunction $\phi_i(x)$). Classical boundary conditions, for which the stiffness and/or the damping of the ends are zero or infinite, lead to

Fig 11 Kinematic (a) and static (b) boundary conditions; viscoelastic (Kelvin-Voigt) end devices (c)

equations with well-known solutions in the literature. When viscoelastic devices are considered at the ends, eigenvalues Λ_i are generally complex numbers which must be searched for numerically since closed-form solutions are in general not available [37, 38]. This issue will be better discussed in the following application.

3.3 Application

In this section, the model discussed in the previous paragraph is used to analyze the dynamics of a simply supported Euler-Bernoulli beam with external damping and endowed with a

Fig 12 Variable x and parameters of the adopted model

Kelvin-Voigt rotational device at both the end cross-sections, see Fig. 12.

The boundary conditions, see Eq. (12), are then:

$$\begin{aligned}
& v(x,t)|_{x=X} = 0 \\
& B \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \Big|_{x=X} = \\
& = H \left(-K_{RX} \frac{\partial v(x,t)}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=X} - C_{RX} \frac{\partial^2 v(x,t)}{\partial x \partial t} \Big|_{x=X} \right) \\
& X = \{0, L\}, H = -1 \text{ in } x = 0, H = 1 \text{ in } x = L
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Therefore, applying the boundary conditions Eq. (13) in the solving Eq. (10), the i -th vibration mode-shapes $\phi_i(x)$ and the relevant eigenvalue Λ_i are gathered.

When the viscoelastic (Kelvin-Voigt) end devices are not provided (that is, when $K_{R0}=K_{RL}=C_{R0}=C_{RL}=0$), the solution is the well-known one:

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi_i(x) &= A_{3i} \sin\left(i\pi \frac{x}{L}\right) \\
q_i(t) &= e^{-\zeta_i \omega_i t} \left[A_{5i} \cos(\omega_{di} t) + A_{6i} \sin(\omega_{di} t) \right] \\
\omega_i &= i^2 \pi^2 \sqrt{\frac{B}{\mu L^4}}, \zeta_i = \frac{c}{2\mu\omega_i}, \omega_{di} = \omega_i \sqrt{1 - \zeta_i^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where ζ_i is the damping ratio, assumed less than one (the usual hypothesis of underdamped structure), ω_i is the angular frequency (whence the frequency $f_i = \omega_i / (2\pi)$) and ω_{di} stands for the damped angular frequency of the vibrations (whence the damped frequency $f_{di} = \omega_{di} / (2\pi)$); mode shapes are reals and the beam is called “proportionally damped”.

When two elastic rotational devices of the same stiffness K_R are considered (that is, when $K_{R0} = K_{RL} = K_R \neq 0$, $C_{R0} = C_{RL} = 0$), the solution can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi_i(x) &= A_{1i} \cos\left(\frac{\omega_{ni} x}{L}\right) + A_{2i} \cosh\left(\frac{\omega_{ni} x}{L}\right) + \\
&\quad + A_{3i} \sin\left(\frac{\omega_{ni} x}{L}\right) + A_{4i} \sinh\left(\frac{\omega_{ni} x}{L}\right) \\
q_i(t) &= e^{-\zeta_i \omega_i t} \left[C_{5i} \cos(\omega_{di} t) + C_{6i} \sin(\omega_{di} t) \right] \\
\omega_i &= \omega_{ni}^2 \sqrt{\frac{B}{\mu L^4}}, \zeta_i = \frac{c}{2\mu\omega_i}, \omega_{di} = \omega_i \sqrt{1 - \zeta_i^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where ω_{ni} are normalized values solution of the equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left(\frac{LK_R}{B}\right)^2 + 2\omega_{ni} \sin(\omega_{ni}) \\
&\left(\frac{LK_R}{B} \cosh(\omega_{ni}) + \omega_{ni} \sinh(\omega_{ni})\right) = \\
&\frac{LK_R}{B} \cos(\omega_{ni}) \left(\frac{LK_R}{B} \cosh(\omega_{ni}) + 2\omega_{ni} \sinh(\omega_{ni})\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

For instance, Fig. 13 shows the variation of the first normalized frequency ω_{n1} with the normalized stiffness LK_R/B of the rotational springs. When this stiffness is zero, the known value π of a simple supported beam is obtained

Fig 13 Increase of the first frequency due to end rotational springs

(see Eq. (14)); when LK_R/B increases, ω_{n1} tends to the asymptotic value of 4.73 of a double-clamped beam. None of the four constants A_{1i} , A_{2i} , A_{3i} and A_{4i} (obviously related by three relationships, since mode-shapes depend only by one generic constant) is null when $K_R \neq 0$; for the sake of brevity, their explicit calculation is here omitted. However, as in the previous case, mode shapes are real and the beam is still called “proportionally damped”.

When two viscoelastic rotational devices of the same stiffness K_R and damping C_R are considered (that is, when $K_{R0} = K_{RL} = K_R \neq 0$, $C_{R0} = C_{RL} = C_R \neq 0$), the solution is in the general form Eq. (10) with complex conjugate pairs of eigenvalues depending on:

$$\Lambda_i = \Lambda_i \left(\frac{B}{\mu}, \frac{c}{\mu}, L, \frac{LK_R}{B}, \frac{C_R}{cL^3} \right) \tag{17}$$

where the last two terms among the brackets are the normalized stiffness and damping of the end devices, respectively. The first three terms are not normalized; however, their choice as system parameters is useful for the following case studies. For a given set of the parameters, the solution can be evaluated with a numerical method [37, 38]. Aiming to recognize the damping ratio ζ_i and the angular frequency ω_i (whence the frequency $f_i = \omega_i / (2\pi)$), the i -th (complex) eigenvalue Λ_i can be also written as [38]:

$$\omega_i = |\Lambda_i|, \zeta_i = -\frac{\Re(\Lambda_i)}{\omega_i} \tag{18}$$

These cases are called “*non-proportionally damped*”. The physical meaning is an energy dissipation no more uniformly distributed on the beam (due to the viscous end devices); the analytical implication is that the solution cannot be searched for with real mode-shapes, but complex eigenvalues and mode-shapes are needed. This result can be exploited to evaluate the dissipative contribution at the edges as the non-proportional part of the damping; certainly, this conclusion is as realistic as the other sources of non-proportionality of the beam are negligible (mainly, noise, non-linearities and localized damages). The percentage of non-proportional damping is defined as:

$$D_{NP} = -\frac{\zeta_i - \zeta_{i,prop}}{\zeta_i}, \zeta_i = -\frac{\Re(\Lambda_i)}{\omega_i}, \zeta_{i,prop} = \frac{c}{2\mu\omega_i} \quad (19)$$

where D_{NP} is zero for “*proportionally damped*” beam and tends to 1 if the external damping c is dominated by the dissipation of Kelvin-Voigt rotational devices at the end cross-sections.

3.4 Case studies

The model described in the previous paragraphs is adopted to recognize the non-proportional part of the damping (see Eq. (19)). The fundamental mode shape of the two bridges is used: mode 1 Ref. 4 for the concrete bridge and mode 1 Ref. 11 for the steel bridge. Both mode shapes are flexural vibrations, in the vertical plane for the concrete bridge, and in the horizontal plane for the steel bridge; therefore, the (flexural) beam model described above is suitable. However, since the latter is a planar model, the analyses are restricted to nodes not aligned on the same cross-section.

In detail, the following eigenvalues and eigenvectors are adopted (where \mathbf{i} is the imaginary unit):

$$\phi_i(x=\{0, x_2, x_3, L\}) = \{0, 0.6943 - \mathbf{i} 0.2114, 0.3289 - \mathbf{i} 0.1564, 0\}$$

$$f_{1c} = 8.850 \text{ Hz}, \zeta_{1c} = 3.740 \%$$

$$L = 24 \text{ m}, x_2 = 12 \text{ m}, x_3 = 18 \text{ m (concrete bridge)}$$

$$\phi_i(x=\{0, x_2, x_3, x_4, L\}) = \{0, -0.4355 + \mathbf{i} 0.6285, 0.5311 - \mathbf{i} 0.2636, 0.8312 + \mathbf{i} 0.1303, 0\}$$

$$f_{1s} = 2.979 \text{ Hz}, \zeta_{1s} = 0.195 \%$$

$$L = 47 \text{ m}, x_2 = 14.10 \text{ m}, x_3 = 23.50 \text{ m}, 0$$

$$x_4 = 32.90 \text{ m (steel bridge)}.$$

The five parameters appearing in Eq. (17) are evaluated through the following procedure:

- L , the length of the beam, is assigned; then, it is a known parameter;
- the normalized stiffness, LK_R/B , and damping, $C_R/(cL^3)$, of the end devices, are initially assumed equal to zero; consequently, the ratio B/μ (among the bending stiffness and the mass per unit length) and the ratio c/μ (among the external damping and the mass per unit length) are initially evaluated considering Eq. (14) and imposing the known values of frequency and damping ratio;
- the normalized stiffness, LK_R/B , the normalized damping, $C_R/(cL^3)$, and the ratios B/μ and c/μ are updated, minimizing the differences among the numerical solution and the experimental data (frequency and damping ratio, together with the known points $\underline{\phi}$ of the eigenfunction $\phi_i(x)$). In detail, the following objective function has been adopted:

$$OF = \|\underline{\phi}_{exp} - \underline{\phi}_{num}\|^2 + (f_{exp} - f_{num})^2 + (\zeta_{exp} - \zeta_{num})^2 \quad (20)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ indicates the norm of a vector.

This procedure has been implemented in Wolfram Mathematica; the solution of the algorithm is intended as the combination of LK_R/B , $C_R/(cL^3)$, B/μ and c/μ which leads the objective function to the minimum value closest to the starting point. It is worth noticing that the scheme is robust, since the starting (initial) point is already a reliable measure of the beam dynamics. Table 1 and Table 2 show the starting and the optimal values of the four parameters

Table 5 Initial and updated parameters for the concrete bridge ($L=24 \text{ m}$)

Parameter	Initial	Optimal
$B/\mu, [m^4/s^2]$	10,531,538	7,898,654
$c/\mu, [1/s]$	4.15934	1.45575
$L K_R/B, [-]$	0	0.88945
$C_R/(c L^3), [-]$	0	0.05533

Table 6 Initial and updated parameters for the steel bridge ($L=47\text{ m}$)

Parameter	Initial	Optimal
$B/\mu, [m^4/s^2]$	17,550,630	17,550,630
$c/\mu, [1/s]$	0.07300	0.00562
$L K_R/B, [-]$	0	0
$C_R/(c L^3), [-]$	0	0.303693

(being L assigned) for the concrete bridge and the steel one, respectively. Using the optimal solution listed in the two tables, the percentage of non-proportional damping D_{NP} , Eq. (19), can be evaluated. For the concrete bridge D_{NP} is 65%, whereas for the steel bridge it is 92%. However, due to the low damping shown by the steel bridge, the latter percentage should be considered less reliable.

Moreover, the results obtained for the dimensionless stiffness of the end devices appear physically consistent: for the single-span steel bridge the optimal value is zero, whereas the multi-span concrete bridge exhibits a non-zero stiffness at the ends, due to the coupling among adjacent spans discussed in [Errore: L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.]. 34

To sum up, the proposed procedure, although applied on a few number of experimental data, has proved effective in recognizing the percentage of non-proportional damping. These first encouraging results show that non-proportional contribution to damping is greater than proportional damping. Further investigations on this topic are in progress.

4. Conclusions

The paper discussed the dissipative properties, measured by experimental dynamics tests, of two different typologies of railway (simply supported) beam bridges (namely, pre-stressed concrete bridge and steel truss bridge). Initially, it has been described the structural system and the experimental setup. Subsequently, a thorough analysis related to the data processing and modal identification has been carried out. Especially, the application of time-domain techniques, like the Stochastic Subspace Identification, assessed to

identify the modal parameters (frequencies, modal shapes and damping ratios) as accurately as possible. Such results have been used to perform a manual model updating of the Finite Element model representative of the dynamic structural behavior of the two selected railway bridges. The second part regarded a deep analysis of the damping characteristics. It is based on the mechanical interpretation of the proportional and non-proportional damping by a simple one-dimensional analytical model endowed Kelvin-Voigt rotational device at both the end cross-sections. To this aim, it has been defined a non-proportional damping index able of providing a percentage related to the influence of the different sources of non-proportionality in the damping matrix (such as ballast layer under the track). The results could be used as starting point to justify high value of damping observed in specific experimental campaigns. The application of this methodology to other case studies could statistically strengthen the results. The results may enhance the code prescription in this area.

Acknowledgments

The research leading to these results has received funding from the Italian Government under Cipe resolution n.135 (Dec. 21, 2012), project *INnovating City Planning through Information and Communication Technologies*.

The results of the steel bridge are part of a project that has received funding from the *Research Fund for Coal and Steel* under grant agreement No 800687.

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